

Research Paper

Effect of European and North American poultry housing design and manure management on ammonia emission factors

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ammonia emission factors
Poultry housing systems
Environmental pollution
Litter management
Emission inventory improvement

ABSTRACT

Ammonia (NH₃) is a major environmental pollutant, responsible for approximately 50% of the PM_{2.5} pollution in Europe, contributing to eutrophication and acidification. Approximately 15% and 30% of NH₃ is emitted from poultry production systems in Europe and North America, respectively. Therefore, it is important to understand the factors affecting NH₃ emission factor (NH₃ EF) from poultry production systems. In this study, we analysed the DATAMAN database to identify and quantify NH₃ EF for different poultry housing systems. The data was classified into four production systems, including broiler production and layer production in North America and Europe. NH₃ EF were calculated for these systems. Results showed that the NH₃ EF from Europe-based layer production system was lower (52.7%) than North America-based layer production system; the difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.0483$). Similarly, the NH₃ EF for broiler production systems in Europe was 43% lower than that for North American systems ($p = 0.0084$). The effect of litter management systems on NH₃ EF was not significant ($p = 0.387$). However, the NH₃ EF for European-based new litter system (where the litter is removed after every flock) was 40% lower than North American-based built-up litter system (where several flocks are reared on the same litter). In this study, the EF from studies published after 2010 was 54% lower than those from studies published before 2010 ($p = 0.007$), probably due to improved poultry production systems. Further emission research on newer, improved production systems is required to accurately calculate NH₃ EF which is highly needed to improve the emission inventorying of modern poultry houses.

1. Introduction

As the demand for protein increases, the intensification of poultry production meets the need for affordable, quality food products (Awasthi et al., 2020). Intensive livestock production systems have several adverse effects on animal welfare and health. There is a growing concern about the environmental effects of gases emitted from livestock production systems. These emissions cause nuisance in surrounding residential areas and have the potential to affect natural ecosystems through eutrophication, soil acidification and atmospheric haze because NH₃ is a precursor of PM_{2.5} (Han et al., 2020; Li et al., 2023; Ogink and

Aarnink, 2003).

This impact is more intense when large commercial livestock farms are concentrated in a small geographical area with a high livestock density (Blunden et al., 2008; Harper et al., 2000).

The primary air pollutants originating from animal production are ammonia (NH₃), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), carbon dioxide (CO₂), particulate matter (PM), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) (Bist et al., 2023; EPA, 2021). Global NH₃ emissions from livestock production are increasing due to the intensification of production systems driven by the increase in meat consumption in the global population. It is estimated that global NH₃

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2026.115425>

Received 7 August 2025; Received in revised form 30 October 2025; Accepted 20 February 2026

Available online 27 February 2026

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emissions will reach 9,300 t by 2100, which is 43% higher than in 2008 (Fu et al., 2020; Li et al., 2023).

In the USA, around 60–85% of total NH₃ emissions come from livestock manure, and around 33% of that comes from poultry manure (Bist et al., 2023; USEPA, 2004). Similarly, 75% of agricultural NH₃ emissions in the European Union (EU) come from livestock production, and 15% of the livestock-based NH₃ emissions are contributed by poultry production (Kunes et al., 2022; Oenema et al., 2007; Webb et al., 2005). Exposure of humans and chickens to NH₃ (>25 ppm) increases the risk of respiratory disorders and can affect the growth rate and food conversion ratio of chickens (Xin et al., 2011). According to European laws, the occupational exposure limit (OEL) of NH₃ is 20 ppm for 8 h, while the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health suggested NH₃ OEL of 25 ppm (COMMISSION DIRECTIVE 2000/39/EC; NIOSH, 2007). Therefore, NH₃ concentration in layer and pullet houses should be ≤ 25 ppm (Bist et al., 2023; UEP, 2017).

The revised Gothenburg protocol focused on reducing emissions of NH₃ and other pollutant gases. In comparison to 2005 levels, the EU wants to cut NH₃ emissions by 6% by 2020 and 19% by 2030 (Directive, 2016). In the EU, France and Germany are the major polluters and therefore have emission reduction commitments of 13% and 29%, respectively, by 2030 (Directive, 2016). According to the EEA (2022), some EU member states failed to meet their NH₃ emission reduction targets for 2020 and need further emission reduction to meet their 2020–2029 emission reduction goals. Contrary to the European Union, there are no clear, publicly accessible national targets for lowering NH₃ emissions in the United States and Canada.

In EU layer production systems, laying hens are usually kept in enriched cage and aviary housing systems because the conventional cage systems have been banned since 2012 based on the Council Directive 1999/74/EC (Sutton et al., 2022). Broilers are commonly reared in broiler houses with bedding material. NH₃ emissions are influenced by several factors that are not related to the single livestock housing system itself. These include bedding material, litter moisture, pH, manure management, ventilation systems, animal diet, animal age, stocking density, indoor temperature, and humidity (Bist et al., 2023). By keeping in mind the above-mentioned factors, adopting poultry litter management practices in poultry housing, such as frequent manure removal (50–70% NH₃ emission reduction), and drying of manure and the implementation of air and biological scrubbers (70–90% and 70% reduction respectively) can significantly reduce NH₃ emissions (Sutton et al., 2022).

The factors of poultry housing systems influence NH₃ emissions leading to inconsistent NH₃ released to the atmosphere relative to a specific activity (NH₃ emission factor (EF)) (IPCC, 2019). Similarly, Philippe et al. (2011) also noted that the large variation in NH₃ emissions from livestock production may be due to differences in the housing systems. Different housing systems have different indoor climates and management practices, and these factors also vary in different regions, which is why it is not possible to have one single NH₃ EF representative of all the poultry housing systems. Therefore, it is imperative to calculate separate NH₃ EF for different poultry housing systems and regions.

The main source of NH₃ emissions in poultry production is excreted N in poultry litter. Poultry production generates a significant amount of manure that needs to be properly managed. Poultry manure is not solely composed of bird excrement; for broilers, it also includes bedding materials that vary according to the farming techniques employed. These materials can be made of sawdust, wood shavings, straw, peanut hulls, or rice hulls (Williams, 2013). Poultry manure differs in its composition, especially its nutrient content and physical characteristics, as compared to other livestock manures. It contains N concentration typically ~ 15 kg Mg⁻¹, which is higher than other livestock manures, such as pig manure ~ 5.1 kg Mg⁻¹ and cow manure ~ 4.7 kg Mg⁻¹ (Drózdź et al., 2020). However, N contents in the manure can vary depending on the diet composition. Typically, N in the poultry manure is present in the form of ammonium (4–20%), uric acid (40–70%), urea (4–12%), and protein N

from feed (10–40%) (Drózdź et al., 2020). Trace amounts of nitrogen may exist in the form of creatine (Augustyńska-Prejsnar et al., 2018). The N excreted in different forms in poultry excreta is quickly hydrolyzed to form NH₃ through a series of microbial degradation processes (Bist et al., 2023; Drózdź et al., 2020). N content and the physicochemical properties of the poultry manure vary in function of the poultry production, e.g., for hens droppings, broiler solid manure and ducks slurry. Therefore, separate NH₃ emission factors (EF) are required for accurate quantification of NH₃ emissions from different poultry production systems. This is also necessary for accurate national emission inventory reporting, which is important to understand the emission trends, for monitoring compliance with emission reduction targets, and facilitating the creation of efficient policies. Improved emission data is also required for the revision of the current Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference document for the intensive rearing of poultry and pigs (Santonja et al., 2017).

DATAMAN is a global database developed under the international project DATAMAN (<https://www.dataman.co.nz>). It includes information on NH₃ and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the manure management chain of cattle, swine, poultry, and other animal categories. The database reports emission data along with specific information such as livestock housing systems, manure storage and its duration, climatic conditions, etc., extracted from peer-reviewed publications, conference papers, and existing databases. This database aims to provide refined EF of NH₃ and GHG for accurate reporting of emission inventories (Hassouna et al., 2023).

The main aim of this study is to calculate NH₃ EF for layer and broiler housing systems and manure management systems in North America and Europe by analysing the DATAMAN database. These refined NH₃ EF for different poultry housing and manure management systems of layers and broilers will help in the adoption of emission mitigation practices and contribute to the improvement of national emission inventory reporting.

2. Methodology

2.1. Description of the DATAMAN database

The DATAMAN livestock housing database (<https://www.dataman.co.nz/>; version 2.0), a global livestock housing and manure management EF database, was recently described by Hassouna et al. (2023). Ammonia and GHG emissions from livestock housing systems over a specific period/area (emission rates) extracted from published literature were converted to emission factors (EF), which represent the amount of NH₃ and GHG emitted per unit of N or volatile solids (VS) excreted, and collated to the DATAMAN database. The units of measurement of the emission factors reported in the considered studies were harmonized for this dataset using the methods proposed by Webb et al. (2021). Briefly, the emission rates reported in kg N/animal/day for N₂O and NH₃ were converted to EF (kg N/kg N excreted) by dividing them by the N excretion rate (kg/animal/day) reported in the respective studies or by default N excretion rate values from national emission inventories. A similar approach was followed for the conversion of CH₄ rates (kg CH₄/animal/day) to CH₄ EF (kg CH₄/kg VS excreted).

Based on the conversion approach, EF were divided into three categories: supplied, derived, and estimated EF. Supplied emission EF were directly obtained from the literature without any further calculation. Derived emission factors were converted to the target measure unit using data from the related publication, while estimated emission factors were calculated using external default data (Webb et al., 2021). This was required when the related studies did not report all the data needed to calculate emission factors per kg N or VS excreted.

Particularly, in the DATAMAN poultry database, emission factors of NH₃, CH₄, and N₂O were collated along with related variables. Variables such as climate zone, bird type (broiler or layer), housing systems, and the poultry housing system factors (i.e., relative humidity, temperature,

number of birds, ventilation system, manure type, manure management, and mitigation strategies used) were included. For further details on this database, see the supplementary material.

2.2. Refining of EF and selection of variables

The dataset was refined based on statistical analysis, expert opinions, and field knowledge. The systematic process of data refinement is illustrated in Fig. 1. Emission factors influenced by mitigation measures were excluded because this study aimed to calculate the EF for baseline, unmitigated poultry production systems to provide a source for the calculation of NH₃ and GHG EF from the poultry housing systems to improve the emission inventory reporting process. The EF obtained from studies conducted under conditions not representing the standard poultry housing systems or at the laboratory scale (low number of birds) were also excluded to avoid bias. Inclusion of emission data from such studies may lead to the over- or under-estimation of EF. Refinement of EF data based on the above-mentioned criteria resulted in a very small number of observations for N₂O (n = 21) and CH₄ (n = 18). Analysing this limited data by keeping in mind different independent factors and their combinations was not possible because either most of the observations were linked to one specific sub-factor, or there were not enough to do a meaningful comparison between different sub-factors. Therefore, the analysis was limited to the NH₃ dataset.

The NH₃ EF were further analysed and explored by using different statistical approaches. Based on the composition of data, and through expert opinion on differences in the poultry housing and manure management systems between North America and Europe, NH₃ EF were classified into four production systems and two regions: i) broiler production in North America, ii) layer production in North America, iii)

broiler production in Europe iv) layer production in Europe. The data was divided and further analysed based on the above categories, as we gained valuable insights into potential data complexities and patterns through different statistical approaches explained in section 2.3. For example, different poultry housing system factors like bird categories, floor types, bedding material, etc., were influencing the effects of each other when analyzed individually, both in broiler production and layer production data. Similarly, the outcomes of the manure removal frequency on NH₃ EF were probably linked to the floor type, which makes it difficult to present robust conclusions from such results. Looking at the layer housing systems, the majority of NH₃ EF were associated with battery cage houses, both in Europe and North America. There was a limited number of NH₃ EF associated with aviary housing systems based in North America. There were no data available from Europe-based aviary housing systems in the database. Therefore, to get an overview of how aviary housing systems affect NH₃ EF, a comparison between the battery cage systems and the aviary systems in North American-based layer production systems was also carried out.

An overview of the number of EF from different countries used in the final analysis is given in Table 1. Around 64% of the total NH₃ EF were from North America, with the balance from Europe.

As mentioned above, four different production systems were identified; the characteristics of these are shown in Table 2.

2.3. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out in R (version 4.4.0) using R Studio (version 2024.04.2 + 764) as an Integrated Development Environment (IDE). Different R packages were used for data wrangling, transformation, visualization, and analysis, such as tidyverse (Wickham

Fig. 1. Systematic process of screening the observations.

Table 1
Number of NH₃ EF values used in the analysis by region and country.

Regions	Countries	Number of EF values	Percentage
North America	USA	88	54
	Canada	16	10
Europe	Spain	24	15
	Italy	10	6
	Portugal	7	4
	Slovakia	6	4
	Ireland	8	5
	Turkey	1	1
	UK	2	1

Table 2
Characteristics of broiler and layer production systems in North America and Europe.

Poultry production systems	Regions	
	North America	Europe
Broiler production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broiler house^a • Solid floor • Bedding material • Built-up litter system^b • No. of production cycles per year (5–7)^c • Broiler retention time in house (~7 weeks)^d • Stocking density (32–44 kg/m²) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broiler house • Solid floor • Bedding material • New litter system^e • No. of production cycles per year (6–7)^f • Broiler retention in house (5–6 weeks)^g • Stocking density (36–42 kg/m²)^h
Layer production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Battery Cage houseⁱ • Slatted floor • No bedding material • Stocking density (474–665 cm² per bird)^j • Duration of flock (78–80 weeks)^k 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Battery Cage house • Slatted floor • No bedding material • Stocking density (750 cm² per bird)^l • Duration of flock (72–74 weeks)^m

^aA house for intensive broiler production. It is usually a simple closed building with natural or artificial light, thermally insulated and forced ventilated. The birds are kept on litter spread over the entire floor area (Pain & Menzi, 2003).

^bA litter management system where the several flocks of birds are reared on the same bedding material.

^c(Moore et al., 2011).

^d(Casey et al., 2003; Lima et al., 2011).

^eA litter system where the bedding material and manure is removed from the poultry house after each flock.

^f(Adaszyńska-Skwirzyńska et al., 2025).

^g(Hayes et al., 2006; Madrid et al., 2012; Pereira et al., 2019).

^h(Knížatová et al., 2010).

ⁱA closed building with forced ventilation and with or without a lighting system. Bird are kept in tiered cages, usually made of steel wire, arranged in long rows. Droppings fall through the bottom of the cages and are collected and stored underneath in a deep pit or channel or removed by a belt or scraper system (Pain and Menzi, 2003).

^j(Anderson et al., 2018; Morgan et al., 2014).

^k(Anderson et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2005; Shepherd et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2000).

^l(Council Directive 1999/74/EC)

^m(Kelleghan et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2018; Rosa et al., 2020).

et al., 2019), *dplyr* (Wickham et al., 2022), *lme4* (Bates et al., 2015), *emmeans* (Searle et al., 1980), *rcompanion* (Mangiafico, 2016), and *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016).

The EF data were positively skewed, which was also observed by Hassouna et al. (2023). Different data transformation approaches, such as log transformation, square root transformation, and cube root transformation, were tested to achieve the normal distribution of the residuals from the models (supplementary material). Transformation was necessary to meet the assumptions of the statistical model, such as normal distribution of data, and to overcome the issue of heteroscedasticity to avoid bias in the standard errors.

Initially, descriptive statistics was used to understand the composition and distribution of data. Linear Mixed Effects models (LME) were used to analyse the effect of different production systems on NH₃ EF. A Box-Cox transformation was used at λ value of 0.333, which is equivalent to a cube root transformation (Box and Cox, 1964) (Fig. S3). The transformation was performed by using the *make.tran()* function to easily handle it while calculating the mean differences. To implement the data transformation in the model, *linkfun()* was used from the MASS package. To evaluate the mean differences, the Tukey's HSD test was used to compare the means of different variables. The reported means and confidence intervals were extracted by using the bootstrap approach. For that purpose, *groupwiseMean()* function was used with 10,000 bootstrap replicates. Residual analysis of the models is given in the supplementary materials (Fig. S13-S17).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. NH₃ EF from broiler production systems in North America and in Europe

The mean NH₃ EF for the broiler production system in Europe was 0.146 kg NH₃-N/kg N excreted, which was 43% lower than the North American system (0.258 kg NH₃-N/kg N excreted; Table 3). This 43% difference in NH₃ EF between the two broiler production systems was significant ($p = 0.0084$). This difference in NH₃ EF between the production systems in both regions is due to the difference in the characteristics of both production systems, such as manure management systems, number of broiler flocks per year, number of days broilers are retained in the houses, etc. However, it is important to note that some parts of our discussion are based on the expert knowledge on emission processes because some of the factors are not given in the publications used in these analyses and, therefore, are absent from the database.

The duration that manure stays inside poultry houses can influence the NH₃ emissions. With the limited number of observations in our dataset, we found a significant effect ($p = 0.0055$) of manure removal frequency from broiler houses on NH₃ EF (Fig. S19). NH₃ EF were 64% higher when the manure was removed after 360 days ($n = 18$) as compared to removal after 40 days ($n = 6$). However, more research is required to draw firm conclusions.

In North America generally, solid manure remains inside the broiler house for several production cycles, with manure from each cycle piled up over the previous cycle (built-up litter system) (Harper et al., 2021). In Europe, the solid manure is usually removed from the broiler houses after each production cycle, with new cycles starting on fresh bedding material ("new litter" system) (Meda et al., 2011; Mendes et al., 2014). Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the effect of new litter and built-up litter systems on NH₃ emissions. A significant reduction in

Table 3
Effect of broiler and layer production systems on NH₃ EF.

Production system	Region	Mean NH ₃ EF [kg NH ₃ -N/kg N excreted]	Lower CI ^b	Upper CI	P value
Broiler production system	Europe [24] ^a	0.146	0.114	0.195	0.0084**
	North America [43]	0.258	0.201	0.322	
Layer production system	Europe [34]	0.103	0.0851	0.133	0.0483*
	North America [52]	0.218	0.165	0.283	

^aThe values in the square brackets represent the number of observations used in the analysis. ^bAlong with the mean, bootstrap 95% lower and upper CIs are presented in the respective columns. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.001$, *** $p < 0.0001$.

NH₃ emissions (~86%) was reported with the new litter system compared to the built-up litter system (Harper et al., 2021; Knížatová et al., 2010; Lima et al., 2011). The higher NH₃ emissions from the built-up litter system are mainly due to the higher N content and can lead to up to three times more NH₃ emissions as compared to the new litter system (Harper et al., 2021). In a built-up litter system, the temperature of litter can also increase, due to microbial fermentation, which then increases the conversion of proteins and uric acid to NH₃ and increases the NH₃ emission factor (Brink et al., 2022a; Coufal et al., 2006; Knížatová et al., 2010).

In addition, differences in the fattening duration of broiler flocks between North America and Europe can be another reason for higher NH₃ EF in North America. In general, the fattening duration of broilers in North America and Europe is ~ 7 weeks and 5–6 weeks, respectively (EU, 2019; Junghans et al., 2022; USDA, 2011). The duration of the broiler fattening affects the total N excretion rate (Knížatová et al., 2010; Mulvenna and Ball, 2024). A study conducted by Wheeler et al. (2006) showed a 52% and 22% increase in NH₃ emissions when the flock was kept for 63 days as compared to 42 and 49 days, respectively. This reported increase in NH₃ emissions is because of higher manure mass accumulated in the houses due to a longer broiler fattening period. However, in our analysis North America which has longer fattening period showed higher NH₃ EF (76%) as compared to Europe, likely due to increase in the N excretion rate with increase in the bird age resulting in higher N load on the manure surface before its removal (Khalil et al., 2023; Mitran et al., 2008; Sonaiya, 1989).

Furthermore, the amount of bedding material used also influences the emissions from the broiler houses. A thin layer of bedding material (e.g., 1–2 cm) (Shepherd et al., 2017; Wheeler et al., 2003) is insufficient to absorb all the moisture and immobilise available N in the manure, resulting in higher NH₃ emissions as compared to a thicker layer of bedding material (5 or 7 cm) (Harper et al., 2010; Nicholson et al., 2004). Fresh manure contains around 75% moisture, which can increase NH₃ emissions (Bist et al., 2023; Cohuo-Colli et al., 2018; Ni, 2015). The use of drier bedding material, i.e., woodchips, dried pine leaves etc., can reduce NH₃ emissions significantly (Metsing et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2000). Bedding material also increases the dry matter content of the litter, which reduces the moisture content and ultimately slows down the protein and uric acid breakdown by microbes (UNECE, 2015). To avoid the higher moisture contents in litter, the use of drinker types that reduce the spillage of water on the floor is important.

According to Brink et al. (2022b) and da Borso and Chiumenti (1998) use of nipple and nipple + bowl drinkers reduces the litter moisture and ammonia emissions compared to bell drinkers. However, no concrete information about bedding materials or the type of drinker was given in the North America-based studies, which makes it difficult to draw any conclusions based on the above-mentioned factors related to the bedding material.

3.2. NH₃ EF from the layer production systems in North America and Europe

The mean NH₃ EF from the Europe-based layer production system was 0.103 kg NH₃-N/kg N excreted, which was significantly lower (52.7%) than the mean NH₃ EF of 0.218 kg NH₃-N/kg N excreted for the North American-based layer production system (Table 3). This difference in EF was statistically significant ($p = 0.0483$). The difference in the NH₃ EF between the two production systems is biologically very important because NH₃ emission from the North America-based layer production is more than double that of Europe-based layer production. As for broiler production, the difference in the NH₃ EF between the two-layer production systems can be explained by different management practices. All observations on NH₃ emissions included in this particular analysis were from studies conducted on battery cage housing systems, which are still commonly used in layer production.

There are generally two methods for handling manure in battery

cage houses: 1) frequent removal of manure (several times a week) by using manure belts, and 2) manure stored underneath the cages for long periods. It was reported that the frequent removal of manure by using manure belts reduces NH₃ emissions (Fabbri et al., 2007; Mohankumar Sajeev et al., 2018; Nicholson et al., 2004). In the current study, a significant proportion of the data used for analysis was from the studies conducted in high-rise battery cage systems in the North America where manure is stored inside the house for a longer period (Liang et al., 2003; Liang et al., 2005; Ni et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2000). Whereas the European data are mainly coming from the studies conducted in battery cage houses with manure belts (Alberdi et al., 2016; Fabbri et al., 2007; Rosa et al., 2020, 2022; Vaicionis et al., 2006), this can explain the higher NH₃ EF in layer production in North America.

Another possible reason for higher NH₃ emissions is the stocking density of birds. According to the (Council Directive 1999/74/EC), the minimum area per bird in Europe in a cage system should be 750 cm², while some of the North America data was sourced from studies where the stocking density was much higher (474 cm²/bird) (Morgan et al., 2014; Shepherd et al., 2015). This can also affect the NH₃ EF because of a higher stocking density, which leads to higher manure volume and therefore N load per m². Under these conditions, manure moisture content remains elevated, which can increase volatilization losses (Homidan et al., 2003; Vissers et al., 2021). Similarly, the number of birds in a layer house showed a positive correlation with NH₃ EF (Fig. S18). The factors noted above for cage systems (higher manure volume and moisture content, higher temperature inside the building due to a higher number of birds per m²) can be responsible for that.

Furthermore, the duration that layers stay in the house in Europe is lower (72–74 weeks) as compared to North America (78–80 weeks) contribute to the higher NH₃ EF from the North America-based layer production system. (EU, 2019; Huang and Guo, 2020; Singh et al., 2009; USDA, 2011).

According to the EU Directive 1999/74/EC, conventional battery cage housing systems are banned in the EU since January 2012, and most farmers moved to the enriched battery cages, which offer more space, nesting areas, and perches (Erasmus, 2013). However, the transformation from conventional battery cages to enriched cages did not substantially improve animal welfare and has been criticized since then by organizations working towards animal welfare (Kollenda et al., 2020). Despite various EU-wide and country-specific regulations, a significant proportion of hens, around 40% in the EU overall, and more than 60% in eastern and southern European countries, are still raised in cages (European Commission; Majewski et al., 2024).

All hen cage systems are already banned in Switzerland, Austria, and Luxembourg. While Slovakia, Germany, and the Czech Republic have all passed prohibitions that will take effect in 2025, 2027, and 2030, respectively. New cage installations are banned in France. (Ghislain et al., 2022). Similarly, in Canada the phase-out of traditional battery cage systems by 2036 is mandated under the 2017 National Farmed Animal Care Council (NFACC) Code of Practice (NFACC, 2017). Considering the potential for battery cage systems to eventually be phased out, aviary systems are probably going to be crucial to egg production in the EU and North America.

The DATAMAN database does not have any information on aviary housing systems from Europe, however it did contain a few observations ($n = 9$) from aviary systems in North America. In order to predict the possible consequences of switching to aviary systems, we used the available North American data to compare the ammonia emission factors (NH₃ EF) of battery cage and aviary systems. The comparison showed that the NH₃ EF from the layer production in the aviary housing systems was significantly lower as compared to the battery cage housing systems ($p = 0.0243$; Fig. 2). However, due to relatively low number of observations from aviary housing systems more research and emission measurements need to be carried out for firm conclusions.

The effect of litter management on NH₃ EF from poultry housing from broiler and layer production systems in North America and Europe

Fig. 2. NH_3 EF from the layer production in aviary houses and battery cage houses in North America.

was statistically not significant ($p = 0.387$; Table 4). Based on the data analysis, the difference in NH_3 EF in broiler production between North America, where the built-up litter system is used, and Europe, with a new litter system, was 40%. This difference in EF is due to the difference in the duration for which manure stays inside the house (For further details, see section 3.1).

On the other hand, the difference in NH_3 EF in layer production between North America and Europe was 13% when manure was removed frequently with the help of manure belts during the layer production (Table 4). However, it is not easy to draw any conclusion from these findings because the manure removal frequency from the layer production systems in North America and Europe is similar. The manure is either removed daily (Liang et al., 2003; Ni et al., 2017; Rosa et al., 2020, 2022) or twice a week (Alberdi et al., 2016; Kelleghan et al., 2021; Tong et al., 2021). However, in the present study, there could be other factors influencing the NH_3 EF from the layer production systems in North America and Europe, such as the differences in diet, indoor climate, length of the flock, etc. Apart from that, frequent removal of manure from the houses is likely to increase the emissions at the storage

stage. It is therefore important to adopt effective mitigation measures such as manure covering, use of additives, and biofilters, etc., during manure storage to reduce the overall emissions (Wang et al., 2019).

Apart from NH_3 , the emission of GHGs such as N_2O and CH_4 is also a serious concern from poultry production. The majority of the emission-related studies in poultry production conducted at barn scale are mainly focused on NH_3 emission measurement, which makes it difficult to quantify the GHG emissions from poultry production systems. Additional N_2O and CH_4 measurements are required before attempting a thorough analysis of N_2O and CH_4 EF for different poultry housing systems and related factors.

DATAMAN database consists of data from different regions such as Europe, North America, South America, Oceania, and Asia (Hassouna et al., 2023), and most of the data, particularly from Asia and South America, belongs to cattle and pig production. For poultry production, these regions are underrepresented in the database despite significant research concerning emissions from livestock systems. It could be because most of the research is published in the local languages and difficult to find.

Table 4

Effect of litter management on NH_3 EF in the broiler and layer production systems.

Production system	Region	Litter management	Mean NH_3 EF [kg NH_3 /kg N excreted]	Lower CI ^b	Upper CI	P value
Broiler production	North America	Built-up litter system [53] ^a	0.243	0.197	0.296	0.387
Broiler production	Europe	New litter system [24]	0.146	0.114	0.196	
Layer production	North America	Frequent manure removal (manure belts) [39]	0.114	0.082	0.166	0.130
Layer production	Europe	Frequent manure removal (manure belts) [32]	0.099	0.081	0.130	
Layer production	North America	Stored under cages [22]	0.355	0.258	0.451	

^aThe values in the square brackets represent the number of observations used in the analysis. ^bAlong with the mean, bootstrap 95% lower and upper CIs are presented in the respective columns.

The DATAMAN database will continue to grow in the coming years thanks to the availability of the database framework and the ability to submit published values to the database administrators.

3.3. Effect of publication period on NH_3 EF from poultry housing

We analysed the data from studies published between 2000–2010 and after 2010 to understand if there is any change in EF between the two time periods in poultry production systems on NH_3 EF (Fig. 3). Our results showed a significant effect ($p = 0.007$) of the publication period on NH_3 EF. Results showed that NH_3 EF was 54% lower in the studies published after 2010 compared to the studies published between 2000 and 2010. This effect of publication period was observed for the EU and North America.

This difference in NH_3 EF concerning the publication period is likely due to improved poultry production systems, as current poultry houses are more technologically equipped. Feeding systems have been improved in recent times, as nowadays automatic feeding systems are more common as compared to pan feeding (Nicholson et al., 2004; Pereira, 2017; Pereira et al., 2019). Feeding based on different phases also play an important role in increasing N use efficiency and improving the feed conversion, because usually crude protein has been reduced and the amount of supplied feed varies based on the birds' growth in each phase (Alberdi et al., 2016; Rosa et al., 2020).

Drinking systems have also been improved, preventing water spilling and humidification of the litter. Ventilation systems in the poultry houses have also evolved. Currently, automatic climate systems have been used instead of manual or timer-based fan operating systems, which might help in improving the climate in the poultry houses, thus avoiding overheating and positively influencing emissions (Pereira et al., 2019; Wheeler et al., 2003).

Nowadays, improved emission measurement methods, resulting in better estimates of emissions. Sensor systems and measurement devices have been improved in recent times, and the detection limit has decreased. Currently, multi-sampler systems and optical measuring devices have been used to get more accurate and reliable emission measurements as compared to electrochemical sensors and acid-trap methods (Kelleghan et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2019; Rosa et al., 2022).

4. Conclusion

Using the DATAMAN database, this study offers a thorough analysis of NH_3 EF from poultry housing systems in North America and Europe. Our results highlight the significance of poultry housing systems and manure management in emission mitigation by revealing significant regional and system-specific variations in NH_3 EF. Because of shorter manure retention periods and more frequent manure removal, broiler and layer production systems in Europe continuously showed lower NH_3 EF than those in North America. Systems using new litter or frequent manure removal tended to show lower emissions, especially when compared to built-up litter systems, even though the overall effect of litter management on NH_3 EF was statistically not significant, which is probably due to other factors influencing the emissions, such as floor type, diet composition, etc. Furthermore, research released after 2010 revealed noticeably lower NH_3 EF, which is indicative of improvements in poultry housing, feeding, and emission measurement technologies. Based on current production practices, these insights emphasize the necessity of updating national emission inventories and Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference documents regularly. Future studies should concentrate on completing data gaps, particularly for CH_4 and N_2O , and assessing emissions under newer poultry housing systems, like aviaries, which may take the place of battery cages in response to animal welfare

Fig. 3. Effect of publication periods (between 2000–2010 and after 2010) on NH_3 EF.

laws.

5. Declarations

5.1. Submission declaration

The work described has not been published previously and is not under consideration for publication elsewhere.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wajid Umar: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Antonio Mautone:** Writing – original draft. **Federico Dragoni:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Mélynda Hassouna:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Alasdair Noble:** Validation, Software, Data curation. **Tony J. van der Weerden:** . **Barbara Amon:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This study was financially supported by the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) through the Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) under the “MELS” project (grant number 2819ERA10A), funded under the Joint Call 2018 ERA-GAS (Grant N° 696356), SusAn (Grant N° 696231) and ICT-AGRI 2 (Grant N° 618123) on “Novel technologies, solutions and systems to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions in animal production systems” and supported by the New Zealand Government in support of the objectives of the Global Research Alliance on Agricultural Greenhouse Gases, as part of the ‘Back to the future: Reintegrating land and livestock for GHG mitigation and optimised circularity (ReLive)’ project. We also acknowledge the European Union, Horizon Europe Innovation program [Grant Agreement No. 101081858], titled “ECONUTRI: Innovative concepts and technologies for Ecologically sustainable Nutrient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water and air”.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2026.115425>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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